

“CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR TOWARDS LAPTOPS”

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE: This research paper aim is to find out that which factor affect consumer buying behavior while purchase of laptop and also know which brand of laptop consumer are most loyal.

METHOD/ANALYSIS: This research is carried out in Fatehgarh Sahib area. The descriptive research done by selecting 150 respondents selected through Convenience sampling who are user of laptop. Data is collected through Questionnaire from respondents and data collected represented by Percentage, Graphs and Pie Charts.

FINDINGS: Dell is the most usable brand of laptop among Respondents. 36 % od respondents are using the DELL Laptops. 86 % of respondents are satisfied with the after sales services provided by the company. 38 % of respondents are attracted by companies with discount schemes. 82 % of respondents suggest the same brand of laptops to the other buyers of laptops. Dell has Better Entertainment Features, special Services, reliability, Battery, Weight & Quality.

IMPROVEMENTS:

Improve the market share companies should work with price strategy, easy availability of product & should provide better quality product.

Pricing should be competitive and more advertisement through modern method be done because advertisement have too impact on consumer buying behaviour.

About the Laptop Industry

The laptop industry has been growing at a rapid rate over the last few years. Some of the major players of the laptop industry are Hewlett-Packard, Dell, HCL Info Systems, Compaq, Toshiba, and Sony.

In this study we tried to find out about the consumer's (Specially the College Students) Preference towards Laptops.

I conducted a survey with the help of questionnaires sample size of 150 of College students and staff. This survey will be taken from the College Students of Fatehgarh Sahib.

Dell

Dell Inc. is a multinational technology corporation that develops, manufactures, sells, and supports personal computers and other computer-related products. The company is based in Round Rock, Texas. Dell employs more than 76,500 people worldwide as of 2009.

LENOVO:-

“Hope through Entrepreneurship” In 1984, 11 computer scientists in Beijing, China had a vision to create a company that would bring the advantages of information technology to the Chinese people. With approximately-\$25,000 used in seed money and the determination to turn their research into successful products

Sony:

Sony is not new to India. Whether it was the television, or the walkman, a Sony always remained a must in the wish list of any Indian, returning home from abroad This love for the brand culminated in a new relationship when inspired by a reform friendly Indian business environment, Sony Corporation decided to set up a 100% subsidiary called Sony India on 16th January 1995.

H.P:

Hewlett-Packard Company (NYSE: HPQ), commonly referred to as HP, is a technology corporation headquartered in Palo Alto, California, United States.

REVIEW LITERATURE

Lee Joo ,SeungHoonYoo and KwakSeung-(August 2010)” In this paper, we analyze consumers' willingness-to-pay for Laptops with the attributes such as the speed of Laptops, , the size of Laptop and price. To estimating consumers' willingness- to-pay for the attributes of Laptops, we apply a contingent ranking method, which makes the respondents rank hypothetical Laptops alternatives featuring various combinations of attributes, to a survey data collected in

Korea. Using the estimated willingness-to-pay, we predict the shape and the ability of future's Laptops and draw policy implications for the national and company level R&D strategies.

Ozok, A. Ant , Benson, Dana , Norcio, Anthony F. (12 Mar 2008) states in their study that Despite their popularity, usability studies concerning Tablet PCs are lacking. This study aimed at determining user satisfaction and preference aspects of Tablet PCs in comparison to laptop PCs and pen-and-paper environments. Several common computer tasks were examined in an experimental environment on 34 college student participants. User satisfaction and preferences were measured by comprehensive questionnaires. An analysis of variance was used for the empirical comparisons. Participants did not have any difficulty in reading, direct manipulation, and form filling tasks. There was a perception of a high number of errors by the participants for the writing task in Tablet PCs. Overall, participants found the general computing capabilities and portability of Tablet PCs impressive. However, the majority did not prefer Tablet PCs to laptop PCs to meet their everyday computing needs. Results can help designers improve the overall usability of the Tablet PC and help its development as a major computing medium.

NEED & SCOPE OF STUDY

Need of Study:

The laptop industry has been growing at a rapid rate over the last few years. Some of the major players of the laptop industry are Hewlett-Packard, .Dell, .HCL Info Systems, .Compaq, Toshiba, Sony.

In this project we tried to find out about the consumer's Buying behavior towards Laptops.

We conducted a survey using questionnaires with a sample size of 150 comprising of College students. This survey will be taken from the respondents of Fatehgarh Sahib.

Scope:-

The results of this study will help understand the consumer's behavior towards selecting laptops as which is the factors that plays a deciding role in the consumer's mind before purchasing a laptop. So, the results will help us evaluate whether the consumers are satisfied with the laptops and services provided by the Laptop Companies to analyze the current marketing tactics are successful or whether some reforms are required in order to increase the sale and maximize the profits.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Objectives

1. To know consumer behaviour while purchasing Laptops.
2. To know that factors affecting consumer behaviour towards Laptops.
3. To know the Brand Loyalty of Laptop Users.
4. To know the consumer view regarding after sales service.

- **Purpose of Study:**

The purpose of this study is to “*Consumer Buying Behaviour towards Laptops*”. A survey was conducted through which an analysis was drowned.

- **Sample size**

“150” sample was taken for the purpose of study and analysis.

- **Target Population:**

The target population is the user of the laptops who are using currently.

- **Sampling:**

The survey is carried out to know the behaviour of consumer in Fatehgarh Sahib.

DATA INTERPETATION TOOLS

Tools are used:

- Percentage.
- Pie Charts
- Graphs

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

Q 1. Qualification of Respondents?

<u>Qualification</u>	<u>No. Of Respondent</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Post Graduate	110	73%
Graduate	31	21%
Others	9	06%
TOTAL	150	100%

Interpretation: Out of 150 Respondents 110 i.e. 73% of the respondents are Post Graduate Students followed by 21% of the Respondents are Graduate whereas others 6 % are related to others education like Diploma holder or higher secondary.

Q 2. Gender of the Respondents?

Gender.	Number Of Respondents	Per%
Male.	99	66%
Female.	51	34%
Total:	150	100%

Interpretation: Out of 150 Respondents 103 i.e. 47% are male followed by 47 i.e. 34% Respondents are female.

Q 3.Age Group of Respondents?

Age group	No of Respondents	Percentage
10-20yr	28	19 %
21-30yr	99	66%
31-40yr	17	12%
Above 40yr	5	3%
Total	150	100%

Interpretation: Out of 150 respondents 99 respondents come under age of 21-30 years followed 28 respondents of age of 10-20 years

Q4. Income Group of the Respondents?

Income(per month)	No of respondents	Percentage
0-10000	98	65 %
11000-20000	37	25%
21000-30000	13	9%
Above 30000	2	1%
Total	150	100 %

Interpretation: Out of 150 respondents 98 respondents are come under income group of 0-10000 per month followed by 37 respondents who come under 11000-20000.

FINDINGS, LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Findings

- ✓ Dell is the most usable brand of laptop among Respondents. 36 % of respondents are using the DELL Laptops
- ✓ 86 % of respondents are satisfied with the after sales services provided by the company..
- ✓ According to the Respondents Advertising Media, Value for Price, Battery Efficiency, Weight are most important whereas Easily availability and colour are Somewhat Important.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are influenced by T.V Advertisements.
- ✓ Dell has Better Entertainment Features, special Services, reliability, Battery, Weight & Quality.
- ✓ Level of satisfaction among respondents towards branded laptop, we made a survey regarding satisfaction level and we find that 61.33% of respondents are Very satisfied with the performance of branded laptop, 24.66 % quite Satisfied, 8% are not Quite Satisfied and only 6% respondents are disappointed with the performance of their branded laptop.
- ✓ 38 % of respondents are attracted by companies with discount schemes.
- ✓ 82 % of respondents suggest the same brand of laptops to the other buyers of laptops

6.2 Limitation of Time

Availability of time was one of the biggest limitations faced. Due to shortage of time we had to limit the work in its present form such as we had to limit our self.

Conclusion

In the conclusion we can say that the DELL Company is growing in the Indian market. There are number of the competitors of the DELL Company like HP, LENOVO, IBM, SONY, etc. But the company is successfully competing with these companies. The Sony is also the leading Brand after DELL.

Mostly the respondents used the DELL laptops due to good feature and effective service provided by the company. Majority of respondents leading to motivate with the help of advertisement by company in newspaper and internet

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